

Kant's Epistemological Turn: Rethinking A Priori Knowledge

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Abstract

Kant's epistemological framework is concerned with analyzing the a priori synthesis principles, avoiding any potential epistemological benefits for the time being. All a priori knowledge must be tested using this framework in order to separate accurate knowledge from false information. It is comparable to a catharsis of all potential mistakes that could exist in the knowledge being examined. In this way, Kant's critical philosophy has proved to be a landmark in the history of western philosophy. Kant, then, moved ahead on the more ambitious task of building a comprehensive system of transcendental knowledge that allows for the testing of both analytical and synthetic judgments as having values or not. He wants to deal with synthetic judgments that are endowed with absolute necessity, which can only be accomplished by a tangible system, as we come across in science. Kant proposed various definitions of analytic propositions. He considers analytic propositions as tautologies. In this paper, analytic propositions have also been explored from epistemological point of view. Semantic definition of analytic propositions has also been depicted in this paper. The advancement is in terms of the addition of the epistemic term *a priori* to analytic judgment; that shows a necessary relationship between the subject and the predicate term. This is Kant's original contribution to epistemology.

Keywords

Kant, Analytic Propositions, A Priori Knowledge, Semantic Definition, Tautologies, Epistemology, Synthetic Judgment.

Introduction

Kant's chief epistemological objective is to look for the possibility of a priori synthetic judgment. I will show that analytic judgments play a crucial role in the manifestation of the judgments. Kant takes this, in the first Critique, as the main problem of pure reason (Kant 19). Pure reason connotes with the totality of principles that deals with the acquisition of all forms of pure and a priori knowledge. The pure reason itself must be critically examined so that our reason may be clarified, and may remain free from all possible flaws (Kant 25). So, Kant's objective here is to set a rigid epistemological framework as a necessary precondition of all knowledge to be obtained.

He was primarily concerned with the examination of the principles of a priori synthesis; keeping himself away, for the time being, from any epistemological gain. With the aid of this framework, all a priori knowledge must be tested so that correct knowledge may be distinguished from the incorrect one. It is like a catharsis of all possible errors that may be contained in the knowledge under consideration.

He now undertakes the greater task of constructing a complete system of transcendental knowledge where both analytic and synthetic judgments may be tested, as containing values or lack of it. He would like to deal with synthetic judgments equipped with absolute necessity, which is possible only through a concrete system that may assure us of providing only a priori necessary truth.

In order to add something to the knowledge, the aforesaid framework must be loaded with the contents by mean of an empirical judgment. The framework serves as an epistemological skeleton which is a necessary precondition of getting knowledge. Nevertheless, the framework has got it's a priori existence, in the form of a given concept. The associated empirical judgment enhances our knowledge concerning the concept. The judgment is, therefore, synthetic; and also a priori, by virtue of the pre-established structure. In this way, Kant's objective of making synthetic judgments necessary is realized. He notes that experiences are themselves contingent, and needs pure a priori principles as essential prerequisite for making experience certain; for a prior knowledge and the terms 'necessity,' and 'universality' are inseparably connected to each other (Kant 5).

In an epistemological sense, experiences are something that can't be relied on. What we know in the name of experience are mere contingent properties by which a substance or an object may be identified. For example, a natural kind term like Aluminium is identified by mean of its malleability, ductility, lightness (in comparison to other metals), colour, etc. However, each of these properties is contingent. So, what is the necessary element that inheres in the substance? It must be something that can't be separated from the very concept of the substance. In Kantian perspective, it must be something like space^[1] that a substance occupies, even when all the external properties of the substance may be taken away. Hence, it is Kant's epistemological contribution that there must be a necessity and universality preserving element that may reinforce the experience.

Objective of study

Kant's epistemic framework is grounded in the notion of synthetic a priori propositions. The objectives of the paper include the following:

1. To examine Kant's epistemological shift from the traditional (pre-Kantian) framework of knowledge;
2. To explore Kant's account of a priori knowledge and its philosophical significance;
3. To critically evaluate Kant's epistemic claim regarding the possibility and necessity of "synthetic a priori judgments."

Review of Literature

In Kant's Critique of Pure Reason (trans. Kemp Smith, 1929), he develops the central thesis that synthetic a priori knowledge is possible through the structures of sensibility and understanding, particularly. Philip Kitcher (1987) reinterprets the role of apriority by questioning the traditional association between a priori knowledge and necessity. Kitcher examination enhances the understanding of a priori knowledge. Lewis (1918) also evaluates Kantian position on necessity and a priori knowledge. Likewise, Ruth Marcus (1947) critically evaluates and challenges Kantian notion of analyticity.

Main Text**Analytic Proposition as Tautologies:**

An analytic proposition may be called as a tautology or a logical truth which, by virtue of its definition, is necessarily true. It may be formulated as: "a proposition is analytic if and only if it is a tautology or logically true; or its negation results in self-contradiction." For example, a wall can't be green and not green at the same time, that is to say, a proposition of the form 'p and not p'.

This definition endorses 'a bachelor is an unmarried person,' to be an analytic proposition because its negation implies self-contradiction. Wittgenstein shows all logical propositions to be tautologies. Hence, all such propositions are analytic. In order to understand a precise account of analyticity, it is essential to clarify the terms like 'tautology' 'negation,' and 'self-contradiction.'

A proposition is said to be tautologous, if it is true on ascription of truth values of its component parts i.e. a proposition of the form 'P v ¬P'. These propositions may also be called as logical truths because they are based on the principles of propositional logic. The term 'negation,' implies 'it is not the case that a proposition is true.' Replacement of 'v' (logical disjunction) with '∧' (logical conjunction), results in self-contradiction, of the form 'P ∧ ¬P'.

The Semantic Definition:

This definition is weak, but significant from Kripke's point of view since his doctrine of rigid designation and the possibility of necessary a posteriori truth is based on the definition of this kind. When Kripke argues that 'Gold is the element with atomic number 79,' he means that the natural kind term 'gold' and the associated description that shows its essential property are, in fact, synonymous to each other. So, there is a semantic sense in this definition.

A natural kind term and its associated description are semantically equivalent to each other. This definition also applies to Kripke's identity statements, e.g. 'Hesperus is Phosphorus,' which involve two terms of the said kind because both the terms refer to the same planet Venus. Similarly, Frege's classic example of identical terms 'morning star' and 'evening star' are synonymous or semantically equivalent to each other because both refer to the planet

So, in what ways the terms are different from each other? Frege answers that both the terms show different senses. According to Frege, sense (Sinn) is the semantic property of a word or a sentence by virtue of which the meaning (Bedeutung) of that word or sentence is revealed. Sense is an ingredient in meaning. The notion of sense explains the utility of identical terms in determining referent of the terms. Both the terms display different senses, in spite of that fact

the terms refer to a single referent. The referent is the meaning of the terms. In Frege's theory of meaning, the referent of a proper name or a singular term is nothing but its meaning. There is no other meaning of singular terms apart from their referents. This is Frege's referential theory of meaning, where the referent is synonym with meaning. In these examples, there is both sense as well as meaning.

There are words and sentences which have sense but no meaning. For example, the words and sentences of a story bears sense (in the context of the story) but are not meaningful, for there are no corresponding objects. The characters of the story, or what Frege calls "work of fiction," reveals sense but are meaningless. Early Wittgenstein was also agreeing with Frege that the meaning of proper names are nothing but corresponding objects. There is one to one correspondence between names and objects. Names are linguistic entities and objects are their factual entities. Names combine to form elementary propositions; and facts are nothing but the combinations of objects. Names have meaning, while propositions have sense. Names don't have sense in this system; while Frege considers both names and propositions as containing sense. Thus, central to the semantic based definition are empirical objects; while analyticity in the Kantian sense involves conceptual objects; as evident from mathematical and geometrical propositions. So, the sense of analyticity in this definition is trivial.

Nevertheless, this definition is significant because critics of the Kantian position from Quine to Kripke use this sort of definition as a base to refute the notion of analyticity. Quine claims that the term 'analytic' may mean 'synonym;' and that's why both the terms may be used interchangeably ("Two Dogmas"). He should be reminded that Kant's uses the term analytic in a technical sense, i.e. the criteria for which has been worked out by him with great care (CPR B4); while the term 'synonym' is a general, and epistemologically trivial term.

Likewise, Quinton shows disagreement with the Kantian position. He argues that there are propositions that seem to be analytic in Kantian sense but results are found to be counterintuitive, e.g. 'nothing is red and green all over' (Quinton 18). However, according to the second condition described above, one has to become conscious of the necessity of the judgment. This condition is not fulfilled in Quinton's example. Hence, the proposition is not analytic in the Kantian sense. Moreover, there seems to be no relationship between the subject term (or extension) 'nothing' and the predicate term (intension) 'red and green all over.' The latter doesn't determine the former. The Kantian position is, therefore, defended.

The first definition is integrated, according to which a proposition may be called as analytic, if it meets the following two requirements:

1. It must be a tautology.
2. Its negation must be self-contradictory.

According to Kant, the fundamental requirement for an analytic judgment is that one need not to go beyond the concept of the subject term so that the explanation of the predicate term may be framed. The former is merely to be analyzed, to meet the later. All analytic judgments are also a priori, as depicted above with the two requirements. The tautology-based definition is more justifiable than the synonym based one; and is in accord with Kantian position. This agrees with the criteria of analytic judgments that Kant prefers, i.e. identity along with the principle of contradiction. In one sense, analytic judgments appear to play the epistemological role to provide a framework that supports the synthetic judgment; and, thus, the possibility of a priori synthetic judgments may be justified. In another sense, a prior element in the judgment has been taken as a genuine source of absolute necessity. The Kantian approach appears to be retrogressive, where we are required to move backward and ensure that the obtained knowledge is essentially grounded in pure intuitions.

Conclusion

Author has shown that analytic judgments, show advancement over pre-Kantian notions, i.e. 'trifling propositions,' truths of reason, and relation of ideas that have been established on similar lines. The advancement is in terms of the addition of the epistemic term a priori to analytic judgment; that shows a necessary relationship between the subject and the predicate term. This is Kant's original contribution to epistemology. The mathematical and geometrical propositions are the absolute cases of this relationship. These propositions depend on pure intuitions, i.e. time and space respectively. The pure concepts of other kinds, however, don't depend on pure intuition, but on the essential properties of an object. It is fair to endorse that pure intuitions are absolute a priori concept themselves. And this justifies synthetic judgment a priori where predicate (that is thought to be outside the concept, yet related to it) term is associated with the

concept under consideration through a spatiotemporal framework; since objects always exist in such framework. Without pure intuitions, the very possibility of synthetic judgments a priori fails because these a priori elements are necessary and makes the judgments true.

It is important to note that analytic judgments are not informative, although they show necessary truths merely by analysis of the concepts involved therein. In contrast, the epistemological status of synthetic a priori judgments offers a unique blend of necessity and informative content.

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